

The Mediating Role of Perceived Managerial Support in the Relationship Between Organizational Silence and Quiet Quitting. A Research in Civil Aviation Sector

Murat SUCU¹, Mevlüt ÜZÜLMEZ²

¹ Dr., Independent Researcher, ORCID: 0000-0001-8951-3045.

² Dr., Erciyes University, Aviation Management, ORCID: 0000-0002-4606-7468.

ABSTRACT: Current enterprises aim to increase high profitability, competitive advantage and market share. For this purpose, the impact of managers and employees is very important. Managers should increase people's motivation by providing support to them. Employees whose motivation increases and whose demands and expectations are fulfilled meet, will make more effort for business goals and objectives. This effort will be expressed in the form of voicing their own ideas, taking more responsibility from their job descriptions, and co-operating with other employees. Thus, organisational silence and related quiet quitting behaviours will be eliminated. This study aims to investigate how perceived managerial support affects employees' tendencies toward quiet quitting and organizational silence, exploring the underlying mechanisms and their implications for organizational performance. The research population consists of lower and middle-level employees working in aviation enterprises. The sample of the study comprises 413 participants who voluntarily participated, selected from this population using the convenience sampling method. This research was carried out with a quantitative research method. The data were obtained through an online questionnaire and analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling (Little, et al., 2007, p. 212). In the analysis of the data, SPSS v27 package software was used for the purpose of pre-tests and determination of descriptive statistics, and IBM AMOS v24 package software was used for SEM and CFA analyses. According to the results of the analysis, perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between acceptance silence and quiet quitting. Also, perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between protective silence and quiet quitting.

KEYWORDS: Perceived Managerial Support, Organizational Silence, Quiet Quitting, Enterprise, Civil Aviation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of organizational behavior, the attitudes and actions of employees play a critical role in shaping workplace dynamics and driving organizational success. Two emerging phenomena, quiet quitting and organizational silence, have attracted considerable scholarly interest due to their profound implications for employee engagement, productivity, and effective communication within organizations. Quiet quitting describes a deliberate disengagement where employees limit their efforts to the minimum requirements of their job roles, abstaining from discretionary tasks or extra-role behaviors (Bhatt, Tevatia, & Joshi, 2024). Conversely, organizational silence refers to the tendency of employees to withhold opinions, concerns, or suggestions, often due to perceived risks or a lack of psychological safety (Shojaie, Matin, & Barani, 2011). Both behaviors can reflect deeper organizational challenges, such as low morale, diminished trust, or inadequate communication channels, which may hinder innovation and operational efficiency. These issues are particularly salient in high-stakes industries like aviation, where employee commitment, collaboration, and proactive communication are paramount to ensuring safety, service quality, and organizational resilience.

Perceived managerial support, defined as employees' perceptions of the encouragement, recognition, and resources provided by their managerial, has emerged as a pivotal factor in mitigating such detrimental behaviors (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Supportive leadership fosters a sense of value and belonging among employees, enhancing their motivation, job satisfaction, and willingness to contribute beyond formal expectations.

In contrast, a lack of perceived support may exacerbate disengagement and silence, amplifying the risks associated with quiet quitting and organizational silence. This study focuses on the Turkish aviation sector, a rapidly growing industry characterized by intense operational demands, stringent safety standards, and a diverse workforce. Employees in Turkish aviation enterprises, including cabin crew, ground staff, and technical personnel, operate in high-pressure environments where managerial support can significantly influence their behaviors and attitudes. Despite the sector's economic and strategic importance, there is limited research exploring how perceived managerial support shapes quiet quitting and organizational silence among aviation employees in Turkey (Deniz, 2024; Kılıç & Saygılı, 2019; Kızılcan, 2023;

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Vural & Vural, 2024). By examining these relationships within the context of Turkish aviation enterprises, this study seeks to address a critical gap in the literature.

This study aims to investigate how perceived managerial support affects employees' tendencies toward quiet quitting and organizational silence, exploring the underlying mechanisms and their implications for organizational performance. Furthermore, the study considers the unique cultural and organizational dynamics of the Turkish workplace, where hierarchical structures and collectivist values may influence employees' responses to managerial support. Through this investigation, the research contributes to the broader discourse on organizational behavior while offering practical insights for aviation managers to foster a more engaged, communicative, and resilient workforce. Ultimately, the findings aim to inform strategies that enhance employee well-being and organizational effectiveness in one of Turkey's most critical industries.

II. PERCEIVED MANAGERIAL SUPPORT

Perceived managerial support is defined as employees' perception of the support provided by their managers (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Eisenberger, Rhoades, & Wen, 2020; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Sun, 2019). It is a critical concept that significantly influences employee behavior and performance. In other words, perceived managerial support refers to the employees' assessment of the emotional and professional support they receive from their managers within the framework of their individual perceptions. Understanding the extent to which perceived managerial support meets employees' psychological and professional needs holds strategic importance for organizations, internal workforce dynamics, organizational effectiveness, and sustainable success (Eisenberger et al., 2001; Kurtessis et al., 2017; Panaccio & Vandenberghe, 2009).

Within the scope of perceived managerial support, various subcategories contribute significantly to long-term organizational success and employee engagement. These include training programs that enhance managers' empathy, communication, and leadership skills; transparent and effective feedback processes; meetings that encourage employees to express their opinions; surveys; and the establishment of other communication channels (Ahmed et al., 2015; Riggle, Edmondson, & Hansen, 2009). A more comprehensive analysis classifies perceived managerial support into four fundamental dimensions: job-based informational support, emotional support, material support, and appraisal support (Van Yperen, 1998; Wang, Kraut, & Levine, 2012).

The first dimension, informational support, refers to the knowledge, strategies, and guidance provided by managers to help employees perform their tasks more efficiently and with higher motivation. This type of support not only enhances employees' job performance but also fosters their cognitive capacities, encourages creativity, and facilitates self-improvement. It further promotes the development of innovative approaches in work processes.

The second dimension, emotional support, encompasses the psychological and moral assistance provided to employees facing challenges such as stress, burnout, and exhaustion. This support includes aspects such as being accepted, appreciated, and respected in the workplace (Bozkurt & Kara, 2024; Demirel & Yücel, 2017; Özdemir, 2020). When managers demonstrate empathy, regulate emotional fluctuations, and encourage employees, they contribute significantly to enabling individuals to utilize their abilities more effectively in achieving their goals.

The third dimension, material support, involves providing employees with the necessary resources, budgets, and other facilities required to successfully perform their tasks. This support may include materials, equipment, time, financial resources, and human capital, either to help employees achieve their objectives or as a form of incentive and recognition (Bhantumnavin, 2003). Additionally, the fair distribution of resources and positive attitudes in performance evaluations contribute to employees feeling materially supported.

The fourth dimension, appraisal support, primarily encompasses activities such as guidance and mentoring provided by managers to support employees' subjective career success. Career support plays a crucial role in helping employees with career planning, achieving development goals, and realizing personal aspirations. Within the framework of social exchange theory, employees expect career-oriented support and development opportunities in return for their performance. By effectively managing career guidance, training, and performance evaluation processes, managers contribute to employees' career advancement (Parker, Arthur, & Inkson, 2004).

Karasek, Triantis, and Chaudhry have demonstrated that the concept of social support, particularly perceived managerial support, plays a critical role in protecting employees from the adverse effects of job-related stress. Social support not only enhances employees' well-being but also serves as a buffer that mitigates the destructive effects of stress on individuals. Their research highlights the necessity of considering the effects of different types of social support—such as coworker support and perceived managerial support—on the relationship between stress and strain. In this context, perceived managerial support is recognized as a key factor in reducing employees' stress levels in the workplace (Karasek, Triantis, & Chaudhry, 1982). According to social exchange theory, which explains the relationship between managers and employees based on principles of mutual benefit and trust, perceived managerial support increases or decreases through ongoing interactions between managers and their subordinates (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Settoon, Bennett, & Liden, 1996).

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One constant aspect throughout history is that when managers show interest, approval, respect, and care toward their employees, employees feel valued in the eyes of their superiors. Such behaviors not only enhance job satisfaction but also increase employees' commitment to the organization. Some studies in the literature indicate that positive supportive behaviors by managers—such as listening, providing guidance, offering assistance, and recognizing employees' achievements—reinforce employees' perception that their managers are genuinely concerned about their well-being (Kottke & Sharafinski, 1988; Onn & Lung, 2014).

However, a lack of perceived managerial support—or, conversely, indifference, malicious behaviors, or the complete absence of support—can negatively impact employees' perception of managerial support. From an organizational perspective, negative managerial behaviors can lead to a range of adverse outcomes, including job stress, burnout, and decreased performance (Claudia, 2018). From an individual standpoint, such managerial behaviors can directly affect employees' psychological well-being and, in the long term, may reduce self-confidence and overall individual achievement levels (Erdoğan & Enders, 2007; Wanyama & Eyamu, 2021).

In the context of perceived managerial support, supportive behaviors and their nature encompass tangible actions that reflect managers' care, investment, and attention toward their employees. For instance, listening to employees' work-related concerns or issues without judgment demonstrates a manager's attentive support (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). Other behaviors that reflect managerial interest and support include providing resources, giving feedback, offering career development guidance, praising, encouraging, creating promotion opportunities, and assisting in task completion (Buys et al., 2016).

Related to this topic, policies such as an open-door approach, flexible working hours, and efforts to protect employees from office politics and excessive demands are among the social outcomes of managerial support, as they contribute to improving employees' work-life balance and overall well-being (Ayman & Antani, 2008).

The impact of perceived managerial support in the workplace has also been examined within the context of cultural differences. Studies based on Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory suggest that the perception of managerial support can vary significantly depending on cultural context (Hofstede, 2001). In particular, employees in collectivist cultures tend to place greater importance on managerial support compared to those in individualistic cultures. This is attributed to the high value that individuals in collectivist societies assign to group membership and social support.

Conversely, in individualistic cultures, employees may prioritize personal achievement and independence, perceiving managerial support as less significant. These findings highlight the need to develop approaches that consider different perceptions of managerial support in cross-cultural contexts. Aligning support mechanisms with cultural sensitivities can maximize their impact on job satisfaction, commitment, and performance.

From the perspective of manager-employee relationships, perceived managerial support has critical effects on employees' job satisfaction, commitment, and overall performance levels (Allen et al., 2008). In organizations where managerial support is high, employees tend to place greater importance on their work, feel valued, and remain continuously motivated by their managers, which positively reflects on overall performance.

Conversely, when perceived managerial support declines, communication among employees decreases, and motivation to work diminishes (Maan et al., 2020). Therefore, the relationship between perceived managerial support and two significant phenomena—quiet quitting and organizational silence—has been recognized as an important topic for investigation in contemporary organizational behavior literature (Akçin et al., 2017; Aruoren & Isıaka, 2023; Galanis et al., 2024; Gün, Balsak, & Ayhan, 2024a).

III. QUIET QUITTING

The first quarter of the 21st century has been a period in which businesses have had to deal with more challenges than ever before. The global economic crisis that emerged in 2008, the Covid-19 pandemic that evolved into a worldwide crisis, and the resulting high inflation affecting nearly every part of the world are just a few of these challenges. However, business experts emphasize that contemporary organizations are now facing a new trend that could deeply impact businesses and even shake the corporate world.

This emerging trend in organizational behavior, referred to as quiet quitting, describes a form of work disengagement where employees do not formally resign but deliberately limit their job responsibilities to the bare minimum, slowing down their work pace and avoiding extra responsibilities that contribute to the organization's growth and development. In this context, employees who adopt quiet quitting exhibit certain negative behaviors, such as arriving late and leaving early, refraining from volunteering for leadership roles, remaining silent in meetings even when workflow issues arise, avoiding responding outside working hours, isolating themselves in the workplace, and avoiding social activities (Yıldız, 2023). These employees do not formally quit but create a significant organizational burden through their declining performance (Bhatt, Tevatia, & Joshi, 2024).

From a managerial perspective, individuals who demonstrate such performance often feel unrecognized and unappreciated by their superiors, which leads them to withdraw from displaying high levels of dedication. According to Gallup's research, the decline in employee engagement is largely due to managers' failure to fulfill key leadership responsibilities, such as motivating, empowering, and inspiring their subordinates (Pratiwi, Stanislaus, & Pratiwi, 2023).

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When examining the emergence of the quiet quitting concept, some sources suggest that the term was first introduced in 2009 by economist Mark Boldger. On the other hand, the Los Angeles Times documented that Bryan Creely, a career coach based in Nashville, and a former corporate recruitment expert, first used the term on social media platforms in 2022. Additionally, the concept has been compared to a previously emerging term in China, "lying flat" (Bhatt, Tevatia, & Joshi, 2024).

In a different source, it is stated that before the emergence of quiet quitting, the term "The Great Resignation" came into play. The Great Resignation concept was introduced in May 2021 by Dr. Anthony Klotz, an Associate Professor of Management at University College London, who predicted that employees would leave their jobs due to burnout syndrome and the comfort of the freedom offered by working from home (Ratnatunga, 2022). After the Great Resignation, quiet quitting has been viewed as an alternative to resignation (Ochis, 2024).

Another source claims that quiet quitting gained attention at the beginning of 2022, after 24-year-old Zaid Khan from New York shared a viral 17-second TikTok video in which he briefly defined the concept. The video described quiet quitting as follows: "You're not quitting your job, but you're avoiding doing extra things. You're still fulfilling your duties, but you're opting out of the hustle culture" (Ratnatunga, 2022).

In this context, it can be said that the concept of quiet quitting emerged between 2009 and 2022 and gained widespread popularity in 2022 through social media platforms, receiving significant societal attention.

Although there are various approaches to quiet quitting, it is generally defined using similar concepts. Hetler (2022), Mahand, and Caldwell (2023) describe quiet quitting as performing the minimum required work or failing to meet expectations. Hopke (2022), on the other hand, views quiet quitting as a natural response by employees to the continuously expanding demands of the workforce. Employees who engage in quiet quitting avoid overtime, refrain from attending non-mandatory meetings, and exhibit a lack of proactivity. Quiet quitters limit their job performance in order to maintain a personal work-life balance, preserve their well-being, and disconnect from a high-pressure work environment. Quiet quitting is also described as an unwillingness to exert effort based on appreciation in the workplace. Additionally, quiet quitting can be seen as an indication of a failure on the part of an organization to establish a meaningful connection with its employees (Ochis, 2024).

Quiet quitting is characterized by employees reducing their work motivation by only fulfilling the minimum requirements of their job (Dominique-Ferreira, Oliveira and Prentice, 2023). This behavior most commonly emerges when employees lose a sense of purpose in their work or feel underappreciated (Galanis et al., 2024; Gün, Balsak and Ayhan, 2024a; Karrani et al., 2024). On the other hand, organizational silence is demonstrated when employees refrain from expressing their thoughts and ideas, typically in organizations with high levels of distrust and negative perceptions toward management. In organizations where managerial support is low, employees' commitment to their work declines, triggering quiet quitting behavior (Atilla and Kılıç, 2022). Specifically, the ineffective use of recognition and appreciation mechanisms by managers increases the perception that employees' efforts go unnoticed. Both of these phenomena can have negative consequences for the long-term sustainability of organizations (Aghababaei, 2024). To prevent such negative outcomes, a high level of perceived managerial support is crucial. For instance, to reduce the frequency of quiet quitting in environments where employees feel undervalued, managers can engage in activities that increase employees' sense of belonging, such as offering emotional support, showing respect for employees' opinions, and approaching them with empathy (Hur et al., 2015; Henriksen and Dayton, 2006). Given these reasons, the underlying causes of quiet quitting should also be considered.

Work-Life Balance: Work-life balance is concerned with maintaining a harmonious relationship between work and personal life. If there is no balance between work and personal life conditions, quiet quitting may emerge. Particularly, Generation Z employees desire to allocate sufficient time for their personal life outside of work.

Toxic Workplace Culture: A poor and unsupportive organizational culture is considered one of the major causes of voluntary employee turnover. A toxic environment where employees are not supported can lead to quiet quitting.

Low Salary and Other Benefits: Historically, money has been one of the most significant factors influencing work motivation. Low salaries and benefits are considered contributing factors to the emergence of quiet quitting.

Failure to Fulfill Promises: Managers' lack of empathy and compassion for their employees, ignoring signs of their problems, failing to keep promises, and not valuing employees are among the causes of quiet quitting.

Failure to Address Diversity and Inclusion Issues: Diversity, equity, inclusion, and respect for all employees, including minorities, have become significant concerns for younger workers and minority groups. Therefore, companies that adopt an inclusive management approach, considering the needs of all employees and minorities, can prevent quiet quitting (Bhatt, Tevatia and Joshi, 2024).

Another interpretation of silent resignation is being sufficiently engaged with work to avoid getting fired, putting in just enough effort to receive a paycheck, and taking advantage of remote work opportunities. This interpretation has been linked to recent studies in psychology, which advocate for allowing individuals to focus solely on work-related demands. The concept of single-focus work demands has been emphasized more following the COVID-19 pandemic. Del Rio-Chanona et al. (2023), in a study conducted between 2018 and 2021 in the U.S., found that as a result of the pandemic, mental health deteriorated globally, leading to higher

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rates of job changes and work attrition. In this context, Del Rio-Chanona et al. (2023) emphasized that both silent and great resignation stem from mental distress (Nikolova, 2024).

Additionally, a different study in the U.S. identified that at least 50% of the U.S. workforce consists of silent quitters. In this study, only 32% of employees were found to be committed to their work, 18% were indifferent, and the remaining 50% were classified as silent quitters (Ratnatunga, 2022).

There are also studies that address silent resignation in relation to Generation Z. Research has shown that social media platforms and influencers play a significant role in silent resignation among Generation Z employees (Ochis, 2024). Furthermore, it is stated that employees do not resort to silent resignation if they feel highly committed to their workplace and believe that their needs for a comfortable life and well-being are met (Pratiwi, Stanislaus, and Pratiwi, 2023). Harter (2022) noted that after the pandemic, at least 50% of the workforce worldwide silently resigned. Alexis (2022), through his research, took this claim a step further and stated that 85% of employees worldwide are capable of silently resigning (Yıldız, 2023).

In a study by Nikolova (2024), it was found that individuals with the intention of leaving their jobs exhibit job-searching behavior. Those with career expectations put in slightly more effort but still actively seek out new job opportunities. These employees are more likely to engage in silent resignation.

These studies highlight that there are employees who may silently resign within organizations and emphasize the need for business managers to be supportive and engaged with their employees. Additionally, it is necessary for Generation Z employees to feel a sense of attachment to the organization and have their well-being needs met. This can be achieved by adjusting human resources and general management processes to meet contemporary needs, creating a dynamic structure.

Silent quitters, who physically show up to work but make no extra effort and fail to contribute to business processes, will negatively affect an organization's financial performance. This negative impact may lead to significant issues such as a loss of competitive edge and a reduction in the organization's lifespan. Furthermore, those who silently resign take their knowledge and skills with them, resulting in a decline in the company's intellectual capital and talent pool. This reduction will likely lead to a decrease in productivity and innovation efforts.

IV. ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE

Silence is considered a virtuous behavior, associated with humility, respect for others, prudence, and politeness. People may choose to remain silent due to fear of embarrassment, confrontation, or perceived dangers. There is a frequently used expression that states, "It is better to remain silent and be thought a fool than to speak and remove all doubt." This approach is believed to arise instinctively due to reasons like survival, career preservation, and job security (Ehtiyar & Yanardağ, 2008). However, businesses have increasingly expected their employees to take initiative, speak up, and assume responsibility due to factors such as competition, high customer expectations, and a greater focus on quality. For businesses to survive, they need individuals who are sensitive to environmental challenges, unafraid to share knowledge and expertise, and capable of defending their beliefs and those of their teams. In this context, although the literature focuses on empowerment and open communication channels, many employees express that their organizations do not support communication or the sharing of knowledge and expertise. As a result, Morrison and Milliken (2000) define "organizational silence" as a situation where employees prefer to conceal their views and concerns about organizational issues (Shojaie, Matin, & Barani, 2011). When employees consciously choose to conceal their thoughts, opinions, and criticisms, it leads to several negative consequences for both the organization and the individuals themselves. Due to managers' failure to listen to employees, these workers may feel undervalued and neglected, leading to lower motivation and job satisfaction. Furthermore, organizational silence contributes to decreased employee engagement and increased turnover intentions. In an organizational context, organizational silence hinders organizational change and development, damages the adaptability of the learning organization and its environment, and serves as a barrier to close communication (Acaray & Akturan, 2015).

Organizational silence was first introduced by Morrison and Milliken in 2000. They defined organizational silence as "a collective phenomenon that obstructs organizational change and development." On the other hand, Tangirala and Ramanujam (2008) defined it as "concealing important issues, matters, or events for employees in a business or organization" (Acaray & Akturan, 2015). Van Dyne described organizational silence as "the intentional withholding of work-related ideas, information, and opinions" (Shojaie, Matin, & Barani, 2011). According to Bowen and Blackmon (2003), organizational silence is defined as individuals not expressing their opinions in organizational conversations and discussions. Morrison and Milliken (2000) identified organizational silence as fears and biases related to the expectation of negative attitudes from managers. The organizational consequences of silence include the inability to utilize employees' intellectual contributions, neglecting issues, avoiding negative feedback, and remaining unresponsive to problems (Nartgün & Kartal, 2013).

Accepting silence refers to withholding knowledge, ideas, and opinions by displaying passive behaviors. For example, an employee may prefer to remain passive, thinking that speaking up would be meaningless and that the likelihood of making a difference is very low (Ehtiyar & Yanardağ, 2008). Accepting silence involves not communicating with others and being passive in every situation

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without expressing one's opinions (Pozveh & Karimi, 2016). This form of silence is essentially synonymous with employees who are indifferent and unwilling to take steps to make changes (Nafei, 2016).

Defensive silence refers to the act of concealing one's knowledge in order to protect oneself and defend against potential problems. The motivation behind this type of silence is the individual's fear of providing information. Defensive silence is a deliberate and non-passive behavior used to protect oneself from external threats; however, it is less passive than accepting silence (Pozveh & Karimi, 2016).

Pro-social silence refers to withholding work-related ideas, information, or opinions for the benefit of others or the organization. For example, an employee may have an opinion about an upcoming corporate decision but may choose not to discuss it with others. In this case, the employee proactively and intentionally decides not to disclose certain ideas, information, or opinions in order to benefit the organization. Similar to defensive silence, pro-social silence involves considering and being aware of alternative decision-making options, yet rejecting the presentation of ideas, information, and opinions (Ehtiyar & Yanardağ, 2008). However, social silence can stem from concern for others rather than fear of negative personal consequences. It is the refusal to express ideas, information, or opinions due to the fear of causing harm to others (Nafei, 2016).

Studies on organizational silence generally link this behavior to the attitudes of business managers and the overall climate of the organization. For example, while employees are expected to voluntarily participate in organizational activities based on organizational citizenship behavior, employees exhibiting organizational silence deliberately avoid expressing their views and opinions. In this context, organizational silence negatively affects organizational citizenship behavior (Acaray & Akturan, 2015). Another study found an inverse relationship between organizational commitment and organizational silence. As organizational silence increases, organizational rumors proliferate, and employees' commitment to the organization decreases (Aeen, Zarei, & Matin, 2014). Several other studies have identified a direct relationship between organizational climate and organizational silence (Pozveh & Karimi, 2016). Another cause of organizational silence is attributed to past experiences and a lack of trust in managers. A study conducted in schools found that organizational silence stemmed from the attitudes and behaviors of school administrators (Nartgün & Kartal, 2013).

In environments where employees experience a lack of trust in their managers or the organization, organizational silence, which can be defined as the preference to remain silent instead of expressing opinions, plays a critical role in the perceived managerial support (Acaray & Akturan, 2015; Henriksen & Dayton, 2006). Especially in the context of leader-member exchange theory, supportive behaviors from managers help employees feel more comfortable expressing themselves (Bagheri, Zarei, & Aeen, 2012; Park & Keil, 2009). In organizations where perceived managerial support is high, employees are more likely to freely express their opinions. The adoption of open communication policies and the consideration of employee feedback by managers reduce the culture of silence within the organization, which in turn contributes to increased productivity at both individual and organizational levels (Hamouche, Koritos & Papastathopoulos, 2023; Katircioğlu, 2024). Perceived managerial support can be considered a holistic tool for reducing silent quitting and organizational silence (Dominique-Ferreira, Oliveira, & Prentice, 2023; Gün, Balsak, & Ayhan, 2024b).

Based on the scope of the research and the information obtained from the existing literature, a total of ten hypotheses were carefully formulated to guide the research. These hypotheses are listed below:

H₁: Acceptance silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.

H₂: Defensive silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.

H₃: Protective silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.

H₄: Acceptance silence has an impact on quiet quitting.

H₅: Defensive silence has an impact on quiet quitting.

H₆: Protective silence has an impact on quiet quitting.

H₇: Perceived managerial support has an impact on quiet quitting.

H₈: Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between acceptance silence and quiet quitting.

H₉: Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between defensive silence and quiet quitting.

H₁₀: Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between protective silence and quiet quitting.

V. METHOD

This research was carried out with a quantitative research method. The data were obtained through an online questionnaire and analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling (Little, et al., 2007, p. 212). In the analysis of the data, SPSS v27 package software was used for the purpose of pre-tests and determination of descriptive statistics, and IBM AMOS v24 package software was used for SEM and CFA analyses.

A. Study Sample and Tools

The research population consists of lower and middle-level employees working in aviation enterprises. The sample of the study comprises 413 participants who voluntarily participated, selected from this population using the convenience sampling method. If

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the population size is 4800 people, 357 participants should be achieved with a sampling error of $p=0.5/q=0.5$ (Yazıcıoğlu & Erdoğan, 2004, p. 182). Data required for the research were collected through a questionnaire comprising a demographic form and scales used to measure the variables. The scales employed in the questionnaire—quiet quitting (Jehle & Schmitz, 2007), organizational silence (Dyne et al., 2003), and management support (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Karasek et al., 1982)—were derived from established studies in the literature with recognized validity. The organizational silence scale consists of three sub-dimensions: accepting silence, defensive silence and protective silence. Perceived manager support and quiet quitting scales consist of a single dimension. The data used in the analysis was obtained through both face-to-face and online surveys between January and April 2025.

B. Findings and Discussion

Firstly, descriptive statistics were performed with SPSS programme after the hypotheses were determined. Afterwards, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted. Correlation analyses were then performed and a structural equation model was constructed using AMOS software to test the hypotheses. Model fit indices were examined and direct effects (path coefficients) were analyzed. As seen in Table 1, among the participants, 296 were male (71.7%) and 117 were female (28.3%). Moreover, most of the participants were between the ages of 25-34 (38.7%). However, undergraduate graduates (44.3%) constitute the majority with 183 respondents. Those who have been working for 3 years or less constitute the majority with 176 people (42.6%); those who are married constitute the majority with 256 people (62%) and finally those who have 2 children constitute the majority with 116 people (28.1%).

Table I. Demographic Information of Participants

		Freq.	Perc.			Freq.	Perc.
Gender	Female	117	28,3	Tenure	≤3 years	176	42,6
	Male	296	71,7		4-7 years	99	24
Age	≤24 years	55	13,3		8-11 years	54	13,1
	25-34 years	160	38,7		12-15 years	38	9,2
	35-44 years	140	33,9		≥16 years	46	11,1
	45-54 years	49	11,9	Marital Status	Married	256	62
	≥55 years	9	2,2		Single	157	38
Education	Primary Education	22	5,3	Number of Child	0 child	199	48,1
	High School	102	24,7		1 child	66	16
	Associate Degree	66	16		2 children	116	28,1
	Undergraduate	183	44,3		3 children	21	5,1
	Postgraduate	40	9,7		≥4 children	11	2,7

Before testing the hypotheses, a measurement model was established in maximum likelihood mode with the AMOS v24 program in order to test the structural validity and reliability of the scales. Before establishing this model, the data were scanned with the SPSS v27 program. Mean values were assigned for missing answers. In order to control the distribution of the data, skewness and kurtosis values were checked. As a result of the checks, it was determined that all scale items showed skewness and kurtosis distribution between -1.5 and 1.5 values accepted in the literature. Based on this, it was concluded that the data showed a normal distribution (Tabachnick et al., 2007).

Fornell and Larcker (1981) listed the criteria that need to be validated for a measurement model as follows: (1) the factor loadings of the statements in the model should exceed the 0.50 limit, (2) for the convergent validity criterion, the variance estimate values (AVE) should be higher than 0.50, (3) for reliability, the composite reliability (CR) value obtained from the variables should be higher than 0.60 and the Cronbach's α values should be higher than 0.70, and (4) for discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE value should be greater than the correlation coefficients between the variables. The results obtained from the model are given in Table 2.

Table II. Measurement Model Analysis

Scales	Items	Factor Load	AVE	CR	Alpha
Perceived Managerial Support	PSS1	,765	0,712	0,961	0,960
	PSS2	,847			
	PSS4	,851			
	PSS5	,855			
	PSS6	,880			
	PSS7	,868			
	PSS8	,901			
	PSS9	,887			

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	PSS10	,828			
	PSS11	,741			
Acceptant Silence	Acceptant1	,542	0,505	0,832	0,838
	Acceptant2	,673			
	Acceptant 3	,644			
	Acceptant 4	,793			
	Acceptant 5	,856			
Defensive Silence	Defensive2	,791	0,730	0,890	0,889
	Defensive3	,881			
	Defensive4	,888			
Protective Silence	Protective1	,712	0,503	0,835	0,799
	Protective2	,747			
	Protective3	,688			
	Protective4	,675			
	Protective5	,723			
Quite Quitting	QQ1	,675	0,599	0,855	0,782
	QQ2	,873			
	QQ3	,685			
	QQ4	,843			

The factor loading of the last item of the quite quitting scale is below 0,50. Therefore, the item was removed from the analysis. In addition, in order to increase the goodness of fit values of the model, the third item of the perceived managerial support scale and the first item of Defensive silence were removed from the analyses. Then, covariance was created between the error terms of the first two items of managerial support and between the error terms of the fourth and seventh items in the model, and the goodness of fit values of the model were increased. The goodness of fit values of the measurement model established to test these criteria are as follows: CMIN = 1189,213; df = 312; $\chi^2/df = 3,812$; RMSEA = 0.078; NFI = 0.906; TLI = 0.911; CFI = 0.919; SRMR = 0.079. These values were determined to be within acceptable limits (Hu and Bentler, 1999). As a result of the data measurements, it was determined that all scale items exceeded the 0.50 threshold, the AVE values of all structures exceeded the 0.50 threshold, and the CR and Cronbach Alpha values exceeded the 0.70 threshold. Accordingly, it was concluded that convergent validity and reliability criteria were met in line with the criteria of Fornell and Larcker (1981). The data including the correlation values of the study are shared in Table 3.

Table III. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	1	2	3	4	5
1.Perc. Managerial Su.	3,66	,949	0,844				
2. Acceptance Silence	2,40	,901	-,393***	0,711			
3. Defensive Silence	2,17	,968	-,463***	,651***	0,854		
4. Protective Silence	3,76	,882	,171**	,115*	-,085*	0,709	
5. Quite Quitting	2,94	,869	-,598***	,495***	,459***	,080	0,774

***p<0,001; **p<0,01; Bolded Values = $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$

Table 3 illustrates the means, standard deviations, correlations between the scales, and the square roots of the AVE values. The square root of the AVE values was examined and it was determined that this value was higher than the correlation coefficients. In this case, it was concluded that the scales met the discriminant validity criterion (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The goodness of fit values of the model established to test the hypotheses are; CMIN = 1862,706; df = 398; $\chi^2/df = 4,678$; RMSEA = 0,078; NFI = 0,904; TLI = 0,905; CFI = 0,900; SRMR = 0,088. Hypothesis test results are given in Table 4 and shown figure 1.

Table IV. Direct Effect Analysis Results

Path	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Perceived Managerial Support <--- Acceptance Silence	-,070	,065	-1,404	,160
Perceived Managerial Support <--- Defensive Silence	-,410	,053	-7,630	***
Perceived Managerial Support <--- Protective Silence	,136	,047	2,619	,009
Quite Quitting <--- Acceptance Silence	,307	,064	5,432	***
Quite Quitting <--- Defensive Silence	,028	,045	,538	,591
Quite Quitting <--- Protective Silence	,220	,042	4,111	***
Quite Quitting <--- Perceived Managerial Support	-,534	,056	-8,276	***

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Quite Quitting <--- Gender	-.042	,071	-.944	,345
Quite Quitting <--- Age	-.053	,034	-1,180	,238
Quite Quitting <--- Tenure	,077	,024	1,701	,089

Figure 1. Structural Equation Model of Study

According to the results of direct effect analysis, it was determined that the defensive dimension of organizational silence ($\beta = -0,401$; $p < 0.001$) had a negative effect on perceived managerial support, while the protective silence dimension ($\beta = 0,123$; $p < 0.01$) had a positive effect. It was determined that the acceptant silence dimension ($\beta = -0,091$; $p > 0.05$) did not have a significant effect on perceived managerial support.

When the effects on quite quitting were examined, it was observed that the acceptant ($\beta = 0.345$; $p < 0.001$) and protective ($\beta = 0.172$; $p < 0.001$) dimensions had a positive and significant effect. Perceived managerial support ($\beta = -0.464$; $p < 0.001$) was determined to have a negative effect. In addition, it was concluded that the defensive dimension ($\beta = 0,024$; $p > 0,05$) and the predictors tested as control variables such as gender, age and tenure did not have a significant effect on quite quitting.

In order to determine the role of the mediating variables of the study, the steps suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986) were followed. In addition, the bootstrapping method suggested by Mallinckrodt et al. (2006) was used to determine the indirect effect power. This method can calculate the indirect effect by creating a confidence interval for the population parameter. In the analyses, the bootstrap population parameter sample size was calculated as 2000 and the confidence interval as 95%. According to Baron and Kenny (1986), when conducting a mediation analysis, there must be a significant relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Therefore, since the mediation effect of the Defensive silence dimension does not meet the prerequisite, the hypothesis was rejected. The results obtained for the rest of the relations are given in Table 5.

Table V. Mediator Effect Analysis Results

Hypothesis	Total Effect	p	Direct Effect	p	Indirect Effect	p	Status
H8: Acceptance Silence → Perceived support → Quite quitting	,394	,001	,307	,001	,087	,008	Accepted
H10: Protective Silence → Perceived support → Quite quitting	,147	,039	,220	,001	-,073	,022	Accepted

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According to the results of the indirect effect analysis, perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between acceptance silence and protective silence dimensions and quite quitting. The acceptance and rejection of the hypotheses formed according to all analysis results are shown in Table 6.

Table VI. Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Conclusion
H ₁ : Acceptance silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.	Rejected
H ₂ : Defensive silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.	Accepted
H ₃ : Protective silence has an impact on perceived managerial support.	Accepted
H ₄ : Acceptance silence has an impact on quite quitting.	Accepted
H ₅ : Defensive silence has an impact on quite quitting.	Rejected
H ₆ : Protective silence has an impact on quite quitting.	Accepted
H ₇ : Perceived managerial support has an impact on quite quitting.	Accepted
H ₈ : Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between acceptance silence and quite quitting.	Accepted
H ₉ : Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between defensive silence and quite quitting.	Rejected
H ₁₀ : Perceived managerial support mediates the relationship between protective silence and quite quitting.	Accepted

Quiet quitting describes a form of work disengagement where employees do not formally resign but deliberately limit their job responsibilities to the bare minimum, slowing down their work pace and avoiding extra responsibilities that contribute to the organization's growth and development. Organizational silence as "a collective phenomenon that obstructs organizational change and development." On the other hand, Tangirala and Ramanujam (2008) defined it as "concealing important issues, matters, or events for employees in a business or organization" (Acaray & Akturan, 2015). Based on these explanations, it can be considered that there is a relationship between organizational silence and quiet quitting. It can be said that our tested 4th and 6th hypotheses are confirmed and compatible with the literature. Also, organizational silence, which can be defined as preferring to remain silent instead of expressing opinions in environments where employees lack trust in their managers or the organization, plays a critical role on perceived managerial support (Acaray & Akturan, 2015; Henriksen & Dayton, 2006). Perceived managerial support can be considered as a holistic tool to reduce silent separation and organizational silence (Dominique-Ferreira, Oliveira, & Prentice, 2023; Gün, Balsak, & Ayhan, 2024b). Another reason for organizational silence is attributed to past experiences and lack of trust in managers (Nartgün & Kartal, 2013). It can be said that our tested 2th and 3th hypotheses are confirmed and compatible with the literature. In order to reduce the frequency of silent turnover in situations where employees feel undervalued, managers can take actions that increase employee's sense of belonging, such as providing emotional support, respecting employees' opinions and empathizing with them (Hur et al., 2015; Henriksen & Dayton, 2006). Thus, it can be said that quiet quitting is related to both organizational silence and perceived managerial support. It can be said that our tested 7th hypothesis is confirmed and compatible with the literature. Lack of perceived manager support may increase the risks associated with quiet quitting and organisational silence (Deniz, 2024; Kılıç & Saygılı, 2019; Kızılcın, 2023; Vural & Vural, 2024). With this explanation, it can be said that perceived manager support will have a mediating effect on the relationship between organisational silence and quiet quitting. It can be said that our tested 8th and 10th hypotheses are confirmed and compatible with the literature. According to the results of the study, organisational silence affects quiet quitting. In other words, if there is organisational silence in an enterprise, the risk of quiet quitting is high. In this case, the expected and perceived support of employees from their managers is critical. Managerial support takes important roles in increasing or decreasing organisational silence and thus quiet quitting. In this context, silence and quiet quitting tendency of employees can be eliminated with the support and motivation by managers.

CONCLUSION

Human capital is one of the most important assets of today's businesses. Human capital is one of the most important elements for businesses to survive in a competitive environment, to increase their profitability and to overcome their competitors. For this reason, employees should be active in business processes, speak their thoughts and take part in decision-making processes. If employees do not speak their thoughts and only do their duties and do not take initiatives that will benefit the enterprise, it will not be possible to achieve business goals. Another important factor is that employees receive support from their managers. Managers should take attempts to increase the motivation of their employees by answering their demands and expectations and should take their ideas in decision-making processes. In such a structure, employees will not remain silent and will want to be involved in all processes. Within the scope of perceived managerial support, various subcategories contribute significantly to long-term organizational success and employee engagement. These include training programs that enhance managers' empathy, communication, and leadership skills;

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transparent and effective feedback processes; meetings that encourage employees to express their opinions; surveys; and the establishment of other communication channels (Ahmed et al., 2015; Riggle, Edmondson, & Hansen, 2009). Also, quiet quitting describes a form of work disengagement where employees do not formally resign but deliberately limit their job responsibilities to the bare minimum, slowing down their work pace and avoiding extra responsibilities that contribute to the organization's growth and development. Studies on organizational silence generally link this behavior to the attitudes of business managers and the overall climate of the organization. For example, while employees are expected to voluntarily participate in organizational activities based on organizational citizenship behavior, employees exhibiting organizational silence deliberately avoid expressing their views and opinions. In this context, organizational silence negatively affects organizational citizenship behavior (Acaray & Akturan, 2015). In accordance with these explanations, if managerial support is provided, employees' organizational silence behaviours and quiet quitting will be prevented.

Quiet quitting is also defined as an unwillingness to make a discretionary effort in the workplace. Moreover, quiet quitting can also be seen as an indicator of an organization's failure to establish a meaningful bond with its employees (Ochis, 2024). In this context, organizational silence can be considered as a precursor and relationship of quiet quitting. Perceived managerial support is important firstly to prevent organizational silence and then to prevent quiet quitting. A positive perception of perceived managerial support may decrease the relationship between organizational silence and quiet quitting, while a negative perception may increase the level of this relationship.

This study focuses on the Turkish aviation sector, a rapidly growing industry characterised by intense operational demands, strict safety standards and a diverse workforce. Employees in Turkish aviation businesses, including cabin crew, ground staff and technical staff, operate in high-pressure environments where management support can significantly influence their behaviour and attitudes. Despite the economic and strategic importance of the sector, there is limited research examining how perceived managerial support shapes silent turnover and organizational silence among aviation employees in Turkey (Deniz, 2024; Kılıç & Saygılı, 2019; Kızılcın, 2023; Vural & Vural, 2024). This study is considered to fill a critical gap in the literature by examining these relationships in the context of Turkish aviation enterprises.

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